

Solid-state dewetting of gold on stochastically periodic SiO₂ nanocolumns prepared by oblique angle deposition

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Abstract:

Solid State Dewetting (SSD) on patterned substrates is a straightforward method for fabricating ordered arrays of metallic nanoparticles on surfaces. However, a drawback of this procedure is that patterned substrates rely on 2D fabrication methods that usually involve time consuming and expensive processes. Nanostructured thin films deposited by Oblique Angle Deposition (OAD) present at the surface a form of stochastically periodic bundles of nanocolumns that might act as a prepatterned template for fabricating arrays of nanoparticles by SSD. In this work, we explore this concept and investigate the effect of three different types of OAD SiO₂ thin films on the SSD of gold deposited on top. We demonstrate that after SSD the particular surface morphology of these OAD substrates tailors the size and the spatial distribution of the nanoparticles that, arranged in a kind of bimodal size distribution, stem from gold located either on top of the nanocolumns or incorporated in between the open pores among them.

Moreover, in the case of nanostructured templates where interconnected nanocolumnar bundles arrange in the form of discrete motifs, the deposited gold gave rise to approximately a particle per motif, which is one of the assets of patterned SSD. Furthermore, the morphological, optical and crystalline structural analysis of gold nanoparticles suggest that the combination of a discontinuous nanostructured surface and the poor adhesion of gold onto SiO₂ induce a kind of metallic lotus effect and an enhanced supermetalophobicity which are main factors controlling the SSD on the surface of OAD thin films.

Keywords: Supermetalophobicity, Nanometallurgy, Ordered disorder, Nanoparticle array, Oblique Angle Deposition, Solid State Dewetting

Solid State Dewetting (SSD) is a straightforward method for the fabrication of arrays of metallic nanoparticles on a substrate. This method is based on the metastability of metallic thin films whose atoms migrate upon annealing to reduce the surface energy, to eventually break the continuity of the films and form individual nanoparticles. Although this process leads to a random distribution of nanoparticles, relevant features such as their mean size, spacing and distribution order, can be tailored controlling the annealing temperature,¹ the thickness of the film,² and the composition³⁻⁵ and morphology of the substrates.^{2,6} The latter modulates the local chemical potential, influences the local diffusion behavior and has demonstrated to be the most versatile variable to generate ordered arrays of particles by SSD. Dewetted metal films on patterned layer surfaces present a *thickness-window* to give rise to one particle per pitch. This thickness range mainly depends on the geometry and size of the motifs and on the interface energy between the metal (or metals) and the substrate. For thicknesses above this *window*, the metal in adjacent pitches may merge together, while for thicknesses below that value several particles per motif may form.^{2,7,8}

Fabrication of patterned substrates with a well-defined structure and a regular pitch size usually involves time-consuming and expensive 2D fabrication methods that can be unpractical for certain applications. In this context, the bundling arrangement of tilted nanocolumns of oxide thin films grown by Physical Vapor Deposition at Oblique Angles (PVD-OAD) offers an alternative procedure to pattern a substrate surface.⁹ Despite their random distribution, nanocolumnar bundles in this type of thin films present an average domain size and a given interdistance, *i.e.* like an ordered disorder, that are determined by the geometrical configuration of the deposition arrangement.¹⁰ The main hypothesis in this work is that, when a metallic layer of a certain thickness is deposited on the surface of OAD thin films and then is subjected to SSD, substrate independent domains offer pits that may match the *thickness-window* and therefore give rise to a well-distributed array of particles.

The accessible porosity and particular surface nanostructure of OAD thin films, acting either as hosts or templates, have been already utilized for the synthesis of well-defined metal particles.¹¹⁻¹³ In these previous investigations, when the metals depicted surface plasmon resonances (SPR), their optical properties were used to unravel the morphology and distribution of the metallic part. This link between optical properties of metal nanoparticles and thermally induced dewetting processes has been also evidenced on other flat substrates.¹⁴⁻¹⁶ However, except for this previous study about laser induced dewetting of silver, the study of SSD of metals on OAD thin films has not been attempted before. In the present work we propose the tailored fabrication of disordered Au nanoparticles by thermally induced SSD onto SiO₂ nanocolumnar thin films templates fabricated by OAD. Three different type of SiO₂ OAD films were synthesized adjusting the geometry of deposition. Then, we studied the effect of surface microstructures on the Au distribution in the as-deposited state and their influence on the SSD after thermal annealing. We have found that the characteristic morphology of the OAD thin films affects the size and controls the interdistance between the gold particles formed after annealing, a relation that validates the use of these surfaces as templates for SSD. We prove that the particular morphology and

nanostructure of the SiO₂ substrate films, combined with the low interface energy between Au and SiO₂, give rise to a metallic lotus effect that assists the SSD of the Au films and mediate the influence of the substrate on the equilibrium shape of the particles. The impact of this result resides not only in the direct application of the particular SiO₂ OAD thin films as supermetallophobic surfaces, but also in the general principle by which surface nanostructured materials with poor metallic adhesion may behave as supermetallophobic. Although a metallophobic behavior has been described before for flat surfaces of MgO, CaO and BeO, and for nanostructured surfaces of LaPO₂, to the best of our knowledge, this is first time that supermetallophobicity has been reported for nanostructured surfaces.^{17,18} Besides unravelling this outstanding behavior of nanostructured OAD SiO₂ thin films, in this work we study the optical properties and texturing properties of Au nanoparticles and prove the feasibility of tailoring their shape, size and spatial distribution by SSD.

Results and Discussion

Growth and morphology of SiO₂ OAD thin films used as templates

In an OAD configuration, as shows Figure 1 a), thin film deposition proceeds through a first nucleation step followed by a progressive growth, where the nuclei shade the regions behind them to the incoming material flux. As a result, the nuclei receive more material than the shadowed areas and the film grows as tilted nanocolumns that may bundle together in the direction perpendicular to the incoming vapor flux. As the deposition angle increases, shadowing effects increase and the columns grow more separated while accessible porosity among nanocolumns also increases. Simultaneously, the size of the bundles and their connectivity decreases at higher deposition angles.^{9,10}

Figure 1.- Schematic diagrams of thin film formation in an OAD configuration (a) and of thin films deposited by this method featuring their columnar microstructure (b) and the top heads of the bundles of nanocolumns formed at the surface (c). Top view SEM pictures of $\text{SiO}_2\text{-70}$ (d), $\text{SiO}_2\text{-85}$ (e) and $\text{SiO}_2\text{-rot}$ (f) thin films. The white arrow in c), d) and e) indicates the bundling direction.

The schemes in Figures 1 b) and c) depict the characteristic features of OAD SiO_2 thin films that are relevant for the present work, *i.e.*, the columnar shape and lateral association in bundles of the OAD nanostructures. In the text, these thin films will be named as $\text{SiO}_2\text{-70}$, $\text{SiO}_2\text{-85}$ and $\text{SiO}_2\text{-rot}$ in reference to their configuration during deposition. The SEM micrographs in Figure 1 d) and e) show that the films actually present nanocolumns laterally associated in bundles that leave open an accessible porosity. As indicated by the arrow in Figure 1 d), $\text{SiO}_2\text{-70}$ thin films exhibit a high lateral connectivity between nanocolumns along the bundling direction and occasional perpendicular interconnections that extend over the whole sample surface and give rise to a large single domain.¹⁰ Therefore, this surface offers a continuous ripple platform with large gaps that restrict connectivity in the direction perpendicular to the bundling. By contrast in the substrate $\text{SiO}_2\text{-85}$, (c.f., Figure 1 e)), the lateral connectivity between nanocolumns is weaker and, even though there is a preferential alignment along the bundling direction, the bundles of columns form small independent domains separated by gaps parallel and perpendicular

to that direction. Meanwhile, it is apparent in the top view micrograph in Figure 1 f) that in sample SiO_2 -rot the bundles of columns don't present any preferential orientation and the nanocolumns grow vertical. This morphology results from the sample rotation during deposition in an OAD configuration making that the direction of the incoming flux of deposited material varies constantly averaging shadowing effects in all directions.⁹

Deposition of gold onto porous and nanostructured OAD SiO_2 thin films.

Top view pictures of Figure 2 show that gold covers the bundles of OAD SiO_2 thin films and reproduce their morphological features. It is apparent that the gaps between hillocks limit the connectivity of the Au film in some directions and lead to the formation of Au patches that are either independent or present narrow connections between each other. As a result, gold forms a branch-like connected structure that is morphologically analogous to that found at the latter stages of typical SSD processes on flat substrates where they have been described as resulting from the breaking up of the rims of growing voids and the appearance of fingers.¹⁹ This means that upon annealing the Au/SiO_2 -OAD samples, instead of going through all the stages of a typical SSD process as occurring for homogeneous layers, dewetting is expected to occur differently because deposited gold mimics the surface microstructural features, is already in a fingering-like stage and may use the thermal energy to directly transform the branches into particles. According to Figure 2, gold connectivity is stronger along the bundling direction in samples Au/SiO_2 -70 and Au/SiO_2 -85 and it is isotropically distributed in sample Au/SiO_2 -rot. The cross-sectional images in Figure 2 clearly reveal the columnar shape of the nanostructured SiO_2 thin films and the limited connectivity of gold in the direction perpendicular to the bundling. In addition to the deposition onto the SiO_2 surface features, some gold also entered the intercolumnar space. Since deposition was carried out at very low pressure, material flux was directional, and the penetration depth in the intercolumnar voids was limited by the tilt angle and separation of SiO_2 nanocolumns. For sample Au/SiO_2 -70, Figure 2 b) shows that, besides the arrangements of connected islands formed on top of the

bundles, gold enters *circa* 50 nm into the intercolumnar gaps. For sample Au/SiO_2-85 (c.f. Figure 2 c), the wider intercolumnar gaps enable that gold penetrates deeper, almost reaching the interface with the substrate. This tendency is more pronounced in sample Au/SiO_2-rot (c.f., Figure 2 d)) because the intercolumnar gaps are normal to the surface. For the three cases, the gold deposited at the sides of the columns appeared in the form of chains of isolated islands that correspond with the early stages of Au nanoparticle growth. For the analysis of the dewetting process, it is also relevant that in sample Au/SiO_2-flat gold forms a continuous film onto its surface (see Figure S1 in the supporting information).

Figure 2.- Schematic diagram (a) and top view and cross sectional SEM images of samples Au/SiO_2-70 (b), Au/SiO_2-85 (c) and Au/SiO_2-rot (d). For the Au/SiO_2-70 and Au/SiO_2-85 samples the cross-sectional images were taken in the direction perpendicular to the bundling. The left and right sides of the cross-sectional images were recorded with the SE and the BSE detectors, respectively. Due to material contrast, the Au appears brighter than the SiO₂ in the pictures. The arrows point out the gaps between bundles in the top view micrographs and the formation of Au particles at the walls of the columns in the cross-sectional images.

Solid State Dewetting on nanostructured SiO₂ thin film surfaces and metallic lotus effect.

Figure 3 presents a sketch and a series of SEM images taken for samples $Au/SiO_2-OAD(SSD)$ after annealing at 900 °C for 15 minutes. Analogous pictures for sample $Au/SiO_2-flat(SSD)$ are reported for comparison in Figure S2 in the supporting information section. The top view micrographs in Figure 3 show that the gold film has completely dewetted from the nanocolumnar SiO₂ thin films and has given rise to well-defined particles. At a first glance, these Au particles are considerably smaller than the nanoparticles formed on sample $Au/SiO_2-flat(SSD)$ (c.f., Figure S2). A closer look to the top view images

in this figure reveals a bimodal distribution of particles in the examined samples. This dual distribution doesn't appear after the SSD on flat substrates.

Figure 3.- Schematic diagram (a) and top view and cross sectional SEM images of Au/SiO₂-70(SSD) (b), Au/SiO₂-85(SSD) (c) and Au/SiO₂-rot(SSD) (d) samples. SE and BSE detectors were used to take the left and right images of the cross section images, respectively.

The histograms of panel a) and their numerical analysis in panel b) in **Figure 4** offer an analytical description of the size and spatial distribution of the particles formed in each case, clearly evidencing the formation of a dual particle size distribution in the form of mesoparticles (~100 nm) and nanoparticles (~15 nm). As a summary, Table 1 gathers the mean particle size calculated from these histograms for both the nano and mesoparticles. Regarding **nanoparticles** (~15 nm), we assume that they mainly stem from the chains of Au islands formed during evaporation on the walls of nanocolumns inside the films and some contribution from gold deposited on the top of the columns that did not succeed in forming mesoparticles (*e.g.*, isolated nanoparticles that were left along the rims on top the bundles). According to Figure 4a) and Table 1, nanoparticles in sample Au/SiO₂-rot(SSD) presented the largest mean particle size followed by samples Au/SiO₂-85(SSD) and Au/SiO₂-70(SSD), *i.e.* the same tendency than that of the gap size between hillocks in the OAD SiO₂ thin films (*c.f.*, Figure 1 and 2). This evidence indicates that gap size controls the nanoparticle size. This correlation is clearly evidenced by the top view images in Figure 3 showing that most nanoparticles have evolved from the gold that was around the gaps. It is noteworthy

that the cross sectional images of Figure 3 still show some Au nanoparticles remaining on the walls of the columns and that, therefore, couldn't contribute to the formation of nanoparticles accounted for by in Figure 4. We assume that this underestimation is less important for samples *Au/SiO₂-85(SSD)* and *Au/SiO₂-70(SSD)* than for sample *Au/SiO₂-rot(SSD)*, where the evaporated gold entered deeper into the gaps during deposition.

On the other hand, we also assume that **mesoparticles** (~100 nm) proceed from the gold deposited on top of the columnar heads and that their formation is mediated by the surface patterns defined by the bundles existing in the OAD SiO₂ thin films. This assumption is confirmed by the fact that mesoparticles depict a narrower size distribution in sample *Au/SiO₂-OAD(SSD)* than in sample *Au/flat(SSD)* (c.f. Figure 4).²⁰ Furthermore, Figures 3 and 4 show that the distinct surface morphologies of the SiO₂ OAD thin films correlate with the differences in size and spatial distribution of mesoparticles, with sample *Au/SiO₂-85(SSD)* presenting the smallest mesoparticle size followed by samples *Au/SiO₂-rot(SSD)* and *Au/SiO₂-70(SSD)* (Table 1 and Figure 4 b)). This tendency supports that the size of the surface patterns defined by the bundling association of nanocolumns is the critical morphological factor tuning the mesoparticle size. We will further discuss this feature in section 3.4. In addition, the spatial distribution of the mesoparticles in Figure 4 b) calculated from their normalized autocorrelation function (Figure Supporting information S4) indicates that the interdistances between them are smaller on the nanostructured than on the flat SiO₂ thin film samples. Moreover, attending to the magnitude of error bars, it can be concluded that sample *Au/SiO₂-85(SSD)* presents a rather homogeneous spatial distribution of mesoparticles, a feature that we associate with singular distribution and average size of surface patterns existing on the *SiO₂-85* thin films acting as substrates.

Figure 4.- a) Histograms of the gold particle size on the different SiO_2 substrates for two different view areas. The dashed curves refer to the left side Y-axis and correspond to the analysis made for the top view SEM images of a $3.50 \mu\text{m}^2$ area in Figure 3. The continuous curves refer to the right side Y-axis and correspond to the results of a similar analysis of SEM images of a $350 \mu\text{m}^2$ area in Figure 3 and for the images of FigureS2 a) and Figure S3. The continuous curve of $\text{Au/SiO}_2\text{-85(SSD)}$ depicts only the size distribution particles bigger than 50 nm and was obtained from the top view image of Figure 3 c). b) Mean particle size and average particle spacing of the mesoparticles obtained from the plots in a) and from figureS4 of supporting information. The mean particle size was calculated by fitting to the standard lognormal distribution.²¹

Table 1.- Mean size of the nano- and mesoparticles obtained from the analysis presented in Figure 4 and contact angle obtained from Figure 5 a). The mesoparticle size for sample $\text{Au/SiO}_2\text{-85(SSD)}$ was obtained by considering only the particles over 50 nm.

	Nanoparticles			Mesoparticles			
	$\text{Au/SiO}_2\text{-70(SSD)}$	$\text{Au/SiO}_2\text{-85(SSD)}$	$\text{Au/SiO}_2\text{-rot(SSD)}$	$\text{Au/SiO}_2\text{-70(SSD)}$	$\text{Au/SiO}_2\text{-85(SSD)}$	$\text{Au/SiO}_2\text{-rot(SSD)}$	$\text{Au/SiO}_2\text{-flat(SSD)}$
Mean size (nm)	10.0 ± 0.1	12.2 ± 0.1	18.2 ± 0.1	320 ± 20	73 ± 5	172 ± 3	530 ± 150
Contact angle (°)	---	---	---	178 ± 3	180 ± 2	180 ± 2	110 ± 2

A closer analysis to the images in Figure 3 reveals that mesoparticles are generally located at the gap places between nanocolumns rather than on the top of the bundled domains of nanocolumns. We assume that his preferential growth on empty voids stems from two energetic driven forces, the excess of chemical potential at the center of the bundles and the minimization of interface energy of gold on these surfaces. The Gibbs–Thomson relation describes the local excess of chemical potential $\Delta\mu$ of a surface as: $\Delta\mu = \kappa \cdot \gamma \cdot \Omega$; with κ the local curvature, γ the surface energy, and Ω the atomic volume. In the case of patterned substrates, γ and Ω remain constant and κ modulates the chemical potential of the surface. In our case, the top part of the surface domains presents a positive curvature ($\kappa > 0$) that,

inducing a positive excess of chemical potential ($\Delta\mu>0$), must lead to the migration of gold from the top of the domains to the rims where mesoparticles grow.

The gold-SiO₂ interface energy is an additional driving force that, apart from inducing the SSD of gold, tends to diminish the contact area between the two phases, a feature that is promoted here by the particular nanostructure of the SiO₂ thin film surfaces. Figure 5 a) and Table 1 show that the contact angles of the mesoparticles with the substrates are effectively much larger on the porous (~180°) than on the flat (110°) SiO₂ substrates, where the contact angle is mainly determined by particle faceting along the (100) and (111) plane orientations (Figure S2 e)). Micrographs in Figure 5 also show that the smaller facet size of the mesoparticles formed on the nanostructured substrates contributes to their spherical shape in comparison with the flatter particles formed on the flat substrates. Making an analogy with *hydrophobicity*, flat SiO₂ substrates would be *metallophobic* (contact angle above 90°) and nanostructured substrates *supermetallophobic* (contact angle above 150°) with the mesoparticles behaving as in a Cassie-Baxter state.²² Therefore, we can assume that the nanostructured films define a metasurface where the poor intrinsic adhesion of Au on SiO₂ combines with the effect of surface asperities that, having a very small size, minimize the Au-SiO₂ contact area and give rise to a *metallic lotus effect*.

Figure 5.- a) Detailed cross-sectional SEM pictures of the mesoparticles formed in the indicated samples. b) XRD diffraction diagrams of the Au/SiO₂ samples before (bottom) and after (top) annealing. Note that the intensity scales are logarithmic in the upper graph and linear in the lower. c) Intensity ratio of the XRD diffraction peaks (111)/(200) plotted in b). The dashed line represents the ratio (111)/(200) in a polycrystalline powder of Au.

Figure 5 a) confirms that the mesoparticles present faceted terminations and a shape typical of a Wulff-state which, normally associated with free standing particles,¹⁹ highlights the little influence of the SiO₂-OAD substrates in the final stage of the SSD. Unlike this behaviour, on sample *Au/SiO₂-flat(SSD)* the mesoparticles depict a clear faceting and some of them evolved to a Winterbottom-type shape (truncated Wulff shape), as expected from their growth onto a continuous substrate.²³ Differences in faceting can be monitored following the texturing state of mesoparticles. According to Figure 5 b) and c), the as deposited Au thin films presented a preferential texture along the (111) plane that is more important for sample *Au/SiO₂-flat* than for sample *Au/SiO₂-OAD*. We relate this feature with the

continuity of the metal film on the reference sample. After annealing, sample *Au/SiO₂-flat(SSD)* considerably increased its texturing degree along the (111) direction, whereas in samples *Au/SiO₂-OAD(SSD)* there was only a slight enhancement of the preferred orientation along the (111) planes. This tendency agrees with that the (111) planes in the fcc structure of gold have a minimal surface energy and are likely to grow faster during annealing, thus favouring a preferential lateral growth of regions with (111) crystal orientation.²⁴ This tendency is partially hampered on the nanostructured substrates because their separated surface domains limit the availability of gold and their size promotes the formation of smaller mesoparticles. Besides, the location of the mesoparticles on top of the gaps between nanocolumns enable the growth of crystalline planes in directions not monitored by Bragg-Brentano XRD analysis.

Tailoring the mesoparticle size and optical properties by SSD

A singular feature of OAD SiO₂ thin films that gives rise to birefringence and optical anisotropy is their anisotropic morphology along the bundling direction.^{25,26} OAD SiO₂ thin film anisotropy might also manifest when looking to the optical properties of *Au/SiO₂-OAD* samples. Therefore, we investigated these systems with polarized light in the directions parallel (//) and perpendicular (⊥) to the bundling direction as illustrated in the scheme of Figure 6 a). In the as deposited state, figure 6 b), spectra of samples *Au/SiO₂-70* and the *Au/SiO₂-85* obtained with polarized light presented remarkable differences that suggest morphological anisotropy in the distribution of gold in these systems (as expected, no anisotropy was found for samples *Au/SiO₂-rot* and *Au/SiO₂-flat*). In addition, the higher transmittance of sample *Au/SiO₂-85* supports that its surface domains are more separated from one another than in the other samples.

Figure 6 c) shows that the annealed samples lost their optical anisotropy, as expected by the isotropic distribution of gold particles obtained by SSD. Remarkably, samples *Au/SiO₂-OAD(SSD)* exhibited a significant absorption around 520 nm that must correspond to the localized SPR absorption of the

smallest nanoparticles described in section 3.2. In addition, the different transmittances in the infrared (IR) region found for the different samples must be related with the large size mesoparticles and their capacity to reflect the electric field of light at these wavelengths.^{27,28} In this regard, the highest intensity of the absorption band due to localized SPR detected in the spectra of sample *Au/SiO₂-85(SSD)* indicates a larger number of independent nanoparticles, while the highest transmittance in the IR region must be attributed to a small size of mesoparticles.

Figure 6.- a) Sketch showing the orientation of the polarization planes of light, parallel // and perpendicular \perp , with respect to the bundling direction. This distinction is missing in the *Au/SiO₂-flat(SSD)* and the *Au/SiO₂-rot(SSD)* systems due to their isotropic character. Transmittance spectra of *Au/SiO₂* systems before b) and after annealing c).

The optical properties of sample *Au/SiO₂-85(SSD)* agree with a narrow size distribution of their nanoparticles, a small size for its mesoparticles and the relatively shorter interdistances existing among them (c.f. Figure 2 and 3). These features call for a more detailed assessment of the morphological features giving rise to this singularity. According to Figure 1 and previous studies in the literature,¹⁰ sample *Au/SiO₂-85* presents bundles of columns that form independent surface domains. Since the deposited gold replicates this morphology, independent domains of the as-deposited gold are expected to form in this sample as evidenced in Figure 2 c). To fully characterize these domains, we used the software IDUN, which applies the morphological operators *Closing* and *Opening* to structurally differentiate elements of the analyzed systems. The *Closing* operator closes the gaps with a size smaller than the structural elements, while the *Opening* operator deletes the regions that can not contain inside

a given structural element. The deposited gold on the microstructured surfaces presents both small grooves, due to lack of coalescence during the formation of the film and large grooves, due to the gaps between bundles. To figure out the independent domains of gold from the top-view SEM micrographs (Figure 7), we applied a *Closing* of 14 nm to remove the small grooves and an *Opening* of 50 nm corresponding to the width of the associated bundles. As a result of the sequential application of the two operators, it appeared that regions separated by big grooves constitute independent domains as shown in Figures 7 a) and b).

Figure 7.- a) Top view SEM image of sample Au/SiO₂-85. The left side presents the micrograph as taken and the right side highlighting the domains after applying IDUN software. b) Plot of the domains identified in a) (warmer colors highlight the larger domains). c) Sketch describing the correspondence between the gold available in a single domain and the formation of a mesoparticle. d) Size distribution of mesoparticles in sample Au/SiO₂-85(SSD) from figure 4 d), and of the potential particles generated from the region presented in a). The potential particle size distribution was calculated by considering that the amount of gold present in each domain forms a spherical particle. This analysis was made for an area of 3.50 μm² and excludes particles smaller than 50 nm.

The scheme in Figure 7 c) represents an ideal case where the thickness of the Au film suits the *thickness window* that leads to the formation of just one mesoparticle per domain. To assess whether such a situation exist in our system, Figure 7 d) compares the size distribution of the mesoparticles presented in Figure 4 b) with the size distribution of the particles that would form from the gold deposited in each domain (we name them “virtual particles”). The similar column plot distributions in this panel reveal that the volume of Au in the domains before dewetting (*i.e.*, in the “virtual particles”) is similar to that of mesoparticles and that their distributions as a function of the domain size are comparable. Moreover, the line represents the ratio between these two distributions and its rather constant value highlights the equivalence between the two column plot distributions. It is also apparent in this figure that there are a few large domains that have considerably more Au than needed to form a mesoparticle (some large “virtual particles” do not correlate with mesoparticles). This indicates that these large patches of gold break into more than one mesoparticle. We assume that this is due to the existence of some necks between gold domains in the as deposited state or to that Rayleigh’s instabilities during annealing contribute to split the gold distribution in the case of the larger domains. Considering a broad approach, the previous analysis proves that in sample *Au/SiO₂-85(SSD)*, an equivalent thickness of 20 nm of Au fits the *thickness window* leading to the formation of one particle per domain.

The singular character of sample *Au/SiO₂-85* is further confirmed by the analysis of the SEM images of the *Au/SiO₂-70* and *Au/SiO₂-rot* obtained applying an analogous procedure based on IDUN. Figure S5 in the supporting information shows that in both cases the as-deposited gold forms a large single domain, which agree with the disordered spatial distribution and the wide size spread found for the gold mesoparticles formed after annealing these samples.

Conclusions

Nanostructured SiO₂ thin films prepared by OAD develop surface patterns that are suitable for the fabrication of distributed arrays of Au nano- and mesoparticles of controlled size. This procedure

represents a simpler and cheaper alternative for the 2D fabrication of nanoscale patterns. The deposition parameters of the OAD SiO₂ thin films serve to tune their morphological features which, in turn, may control the SSD of gold and the formation of a bimodal particle size distribution after annealing. Nanoparticles formation (around 15 nm) is determined by the open porosity provided by the gaps between nanocolumns, while mesoparticles (size around or larger than 100 nm) can be tailored by the size of the bundled arrays of nanocolumns existing in some of the SiO₂ thin films. When the bundles of thin film nanocolumns form independent and isolated surface domains and the thickness of the deposited gold matches the *thickness window*, we prove that after annealing it is possible to approximately produce one mesoparticle per domain. Furthermore, the finding of Wulff-shaped mesoparticles with wetting contact angles around 180° as in a Cassie-Baxter state supports the supermetallophobic character of the investigated surfaces and the occurrence of a metallic *lotus effect* during Solid State Dewetting. To the best of our knowledge, this supermetallophobicity has been described in the present work for the first time. The optical response before annealing shows that systems with an anisotropic lateral bundling association present dichroism before dewetting. After the annealing process, the transmittance rises due to gold coarsening and the appearance of a LSPR absorption associated with the formation of nanoparticles. At this state, the mesoparticles act as independent island of gold and their size set the reflectivity in the IR region of the spectrum.

Material and Methods

Fabrication of SiO₂ OAD thin films and deposition of gold.

Highly porous and mechanically stable nanocolumnar SiO₂ thin films were deposited by electron beam evaporation at Oblique Angle (OAD). SiO₂ pellets supplied by Kurt Lesker (purity 99.99%) were used as targets for this deposition experiment. Figure 1 a) shows a sketch of the experimental configuration used for the OAD deposition of thin films. Distance between substrates and target was approximately 50 cm. An oxygen pressure of approximately 10⁻⁴ mbar was maintained inside the chamber during the

deposition to keep the SiO₂ stoichiometry for the deposited oxide. Three different SiO₂ thin films were grown at oblique zenithal angles (α) of 70° and 85°, and at 70° on a substrate rotating azimuthally (ϕ) at a rate of 20 revolutions per minute. For comparison, to study SSD on flat substrates, compact layers of SiO₂ were grown in the same preparation. In the text, these thin films were named as *SiO₂-70*, *SiO₂-85* and *SiO₂-rot*. They were deposited on Si wafers and on quartz glass plates to allow a straightforward morphological and optical characterization of samples. The thicknesses of SiO₂ thin films, which differ for each configuration and deposition conditions, were set at 350 nm for the *SiO₂-70* samples (note that the thickness of the SiO₂ films depends on the deposition angle because of the different amount of material that reaches the substrates at each zenithal angular configuration).⁹

On top of the SiO₂ films, a layer with an equivalent thickness of 20 nm of gold (as determined on a flat substrate) was evaporated by electron beam in a normal configuration and at a pressure of $1 \cdot 10^{-6}$ mbar. These samples were named *Au/SiO₂-70*, *Au/SiO₂-85*, *Au/SiO₂-rot*, and *Au/SiO₂-flat*, this latter for a reference sample where gold was deposited on a compact and flat SiO₂ thin film prepared by evaporation in normal geometry.

Annealing treatment

To induce a complete SSD of the deposited gold from the SiO₂ thin films, samples were annealed in a tube furnace (Nabertherm, model R70/300/13/S) at 900 °C for 15 minutes in an Ar atmosphere. The resulting sample was designated as (SSD) to indicate that they were annealed, *e.g.*, *Au/SiO₂-70(SSD)*.

Characterization

Top view and cross-sectional Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) images of the *SiO₂* and *Au/SiO₂* thin film samples deposited on Si wafers were taken in a Zeiss FIB Auriga 60 Crossbeam before and after the annealing process. The SEM images were taken at 5 keV primary beam energy, while secondary electron

(SE) and back scattered electron (BSE) images were used for topographic and compositional information, respectively.

The features of the gold samples before dewetting were highlighted and analyzed by the treatment softwares of SEM images IDUN¹⁰ and ImageJ, respectively. ImageJ software was used to measure the size and the contact angle of the particles from top view and cross-sectional SEM images, respectively. IDUN is a MatLAB-based software for SEM pictures analysis that is particularly suited for the detection of unconnected regions in structured thin films. It allows to set the brightness and contrast of an image and, after transforming it into a black and white binary map, apply the mathematical morphology operators *Closing*, which consist of the subsequent application of fundamental operators *Dilation* and *Erosion*, and *Opening*, which consist of the application of *Erosion* and *Dilation*.²⁹ These operators apply a basic structuring element, which is a disk in the case of IDUN. The operator *Dilation* dilates the borders of the elements in the image to the size of the structuring unit. In turn, the operator *Erosion* erodes these borders by the size of the structuring element. In this way, the effect of the operator *Closing* consists of closing the gaps of features with sizes smaller than the structuring element, while the effect of the operator *Opening* consists of deleting the regions that cannot contain inside a given structuring element. The application of these operators removes the unconnected regions of a microstructured thin film from a SEM picture. Then, *ImageJ* was used to count and measure the area of the resultant independent regions determined with *IDUN*.

X-Ray-Diffraction scans in the range 35° to 47° were taken in a Siemens XRD D-5000 set up in the Bragg-Brentano (BB) configuration using the Cu K α radiation at 40 kV in a parallel beam optics.

UV-Visible-NIR transmission spectra of the samples prepared on fused silica substrates were recorded before and after annealing using a Cary 5000 spectrophotometer at normal incidence in the range from 250 nm to 1250 nm.

Supporting Information

The supporting information is available free of charge *via* the Internet at <http://pubs.acs.org>.

It contains the analysis of the solid state dewetting of a gold thin film on a flat substrate; top view SEM images of large overviews of the flat and the nanostructured substrates after annealing and their normalized autocorrelation functions; analysis of the independent domains of the samples *Au/SiO₂-70* and *Au/SiO₂-rot* with the software IDUN.

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